

The Hidden Toll: Demographic and Socio Economic Costs of HIV/AIDS on Families in Benue State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the demographic, social, and economic effects of HIV/AIDS on families in Benue State, Nigeria. The research focused on individuals diagnosed as HIV-positive (People Living with HIV/AIDS, PLWHA) who are actively undergoing care and treatment at selected hospitals. The study ascertain the demographic, social and economic characteristics of people living with HIV/AIDS as well as the effects of HIV/AIDS on the demography and socio-economic development of the study area. The study included both public and private healthcare facilities involved in HIV/AIDS care and a total of 61,679 HIV-positive individuals registered across these facilities. Data were gathered from a sample of 397 respondents across eight selected hospitals determined using the Yamane formula for sample size determination. Data were collected through questionnaires administered to PLWHA, covering personal characteristics such as age, sex, marital status, occupation, and income, along with contributing factors to HIV transmission, including unprotected sex, multiple sexual partners, and needle sharing. Additionally, data on HIV/AIDS-related deaths and case fatality rates were obtained from hospital records. The study revealed significant demographic impacts, including rising infant and child mortality (99.3%), adult mortality (98.3%), and a gender imbalance (97.3%). Socially, there was a marked increase in the number of orphans (94%) and disruptions in marital relationships (93.0%), while economically, HIV/AIDS contributed to a decline in agricultural production (98.8%), food scarcity (98.8%), and rural-urban poverty (98.3%). The study emphasizes the need for targeted policy interventions, including strengthening healthcare systems, supporting orphans, improving economic conditions for affected households, and ensuring gender-sensitive programs. These findings provide vital insights for addressing the ongoing HIV/AIDS challenges in the region, offering evidence to guide future healthcare policies and interventions.

Keywords: Demographic Effects, Socio-economic Impacts, Benue State, People Living with HIV/AIDS, Health Systems.

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1. Introduction

HIV/AIDS, malaria, and tuberculosis are among the deadliest communicable diseases globally, contributing significantly to the burden on public health systems (Dye, 2014). HIV/AIDS, in particular, remains one of the most severe global health crises, with widespread transmission across all countries. Since its emergence, the disease has claimed an estimated 42.3 million lives and continues to impact millions. As of 2023, approximately 39.9 million people were living with HIV worldwide, with 65% of this population residing in the African region. The disease claimed the lives of around 630,000 people in 2023 alone, while an estimated 1.3 million people were newly infected (WHO, 2024). Despite a decrease in new infections in many regions, the global proportion of adults living with HIV has remained constant at approximately 0.8% since 2000 (UNAIDS, 2009).

Sub-Saharan Africa remains the epicenter of the HIV/AIDS epidemic, bearing the highest prevalence of the disease worldwide. This region has seen a reversal of life expectancy gains due to the high mortality rate associated with HIV/AIDS. The epidemic has led to the orphaning of millions of children, with severe socio-economic and demographic consequences. In this context, Nigeria, like many other African countries, has been deeply affected by the HIV/AIDS crisis. In 2023, Nigeria had a national HIV prevalence rate of 3.1%, with some states, including Benue, experiencing even higher rates (UNAIDS, 2009; NACA, 2020).

Benue State, located in central Nigeria, has one of the highest HIV prevalence rates in the country, with the rate standing at 4.9% in recent reports (Jwanle et al., 2023). This rate is alarmingly high and has significant implications for the demographic and socio-economic structure of the state. Despite a reduction from previous years, the HIV burden in Benue State remains substantial, with an estimated 184,745 people living with HIV (PLHIV). The state's HIV prevalence is a contributing factor to the widespread demographic shifts in family structures, especially in rural communities where over 70% of the population resides. The effects of HIV/AIDS on these communities are manifold, influencing everything from household composition to economic productivity and social dynamics.

This epidemic is not only a health crisis but also a threat to the very fabric of society. It affects a nation's economy, disrupts family life, and strains public health infrastructure. The loss of economically active individuals, particularly those in the critical age group of 15 to 49 years, has devastating consequences. Many families face the financial burden of medical care and funerals, while others cope with the loss of breadwinners and the increasing responsibility of raising orphaned children. Moreover, rural households are particularly vulnerable due to the already strained agricultural economy and limited access to healthcare resources (Leal-Filho, et al, 2020).

HIV/AIDS has also exacerbated existing socio-economic challenges in Benue State, including poverty, food insecurity, and a weakened workforce. The epidemic has led to the depletion of human capital, as skilled workers, including health personnel and educators, fall ill or die. These challenges are compounded by the changing patterns of social behavior, such as risky sexual practices during funeral ceremonies, which further fuel the spread of the disease (UNAIDS, 2009). The high mobility of people involved in agricultural trade—such as women and young men in rural Benue—is another factor contributing to the disease’s spread in these regions. Long-distance truck drivers and traders, often spending several days in rural areas, further exacerbate the situation.

The traditional care giving systems in Benue State, which have historically provided support for the sick and elderly, are rapidly deteriorating. Urbanization, the rise of nuclear families, and increasing participation of women in the workforce has all contributed to this decline. With the increasing mortality of younger generations due to HIV/AIDS, older individuals, particularly in rural areas, are left without caregivers, further deepening the socio-economic crisis (UNAIDS, 2009).

This study seeks to examine the demographic, social, and economic effects of HIV/AIDS on families in Benue State, Nigeria. The study is motivated by the alarming HIV prevalence rates in the region, which remain among the highest in the country. The State has a prevalent rate of 4.9% while Nigeria has 1.3% (NACA, 2023 and Jwanle et. al, 2023). The research aims to explore how the epidemic has disrupted family structures, economic activities, and social services, particularly in rural communities. There is a gap in existing literature regarding the specific socio-economic and demographic impacts of HIV/AIDS at the state level. While many studies (Jwanle, Ibiloye, Obaje, Ngwoke, Usha, Amoo, Ogunsola, Okezie, Olaitan, Ofuche, Onwuatuelo, Samuels, Fagbamigbe, Nwagagbo, Ogbanufe, Okoye and Okonkw (2023); Abu, and Kotur (2022); Kwanga, Ikyernum, Enefu, and Makyur (2021); Abua, Ekele and Agbulu (2016), Hilhorst, Liere, Ode and Koning (2006)) have focused on national or broad regional trends, the effects of HIV/AIDS on Benue State’s unique socio-economic and demographic conditions have not been adequately investigated. Understanding the implications of the disease on local communities is essential for tailoring effective interventions and policies that address the specific needs of the state.

The socio-economic landscape in Benue State, characterized by high poverty levels, poor health infrastructure, and limited access to care, has made it more challenging to address the HIV/AIDS epidemic. The rural communities, which are at the forefront of the epidemic, face additional challenges due to food insecurity and limited access to health services. As the food basket of Nigeria, Benue State plays a crucial role in the country’s agricultural production. The movement of agricultural goods and people across rural areas, often involving young men

and women, contributes to the spread of HIV/AIDS in these communities. These factors underscore the urgent need to study the demographic and socio-economic effects of the disease in Benue State.

In conclusion, this research aims to provide a detailed understanding of the impact of HIV/AIDS on the families of Eastern Benue State, with a focus on the socio-economic and demographic consequences. This study will contribute to the broader conversation on the HIV/AIDS epidemic by addressing the specific needs and challenges faced by Benue State, thus informing future interventions and policies for improving public health and development outcomes in the region.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

Sub-Saharan Africa remains the region most affected by the HIV/AIDS epidemic, with some of the highest HIV prevalence rates globally. Despite advancements in some countries like South Africa, which has made strides in vital event registration, no country in the region has achieved complete and accurate coverage of vital statistics, such as birth and death records. The emergence of HIV/AIDS has made this task even more challenging, especially given the high number of deaths attributed to the disease. Accurate data on HIV/AIDS-related mortality remains elusive, complicating efforts to fully understand the scope of the epidemic, its impact on mortality rates, and the broader socio-economic effects, particularly in rural communities. The prevalence of HIV/AIDS in Sub-Saharan Africa has led to an alarming picture of demographic and socio-economic consequences that continue to evolve as the epidemic unfolds.

A significant body of literature has emerged to document the devastation caused by HIV/AIDS, with an increasing focus on not only prevention but also the need for effective treatment and a permanent cure. In Nigeria, sentinel surveys over the years have shown a steady progression in the country's HIV prevalence, with figures reaching 5.4% in 1999, 5.8% in 2001, 4.6% in 2008, and 3.1% in 2013 (Bakare, 2022). Although concerted efforts have helped reduce the national prevalence rate, Nigeria remains heavily affected due to its large population and the inadequacy of screening facilities and reporting mechanisms. HIV/AIDS has also overtaken malaria as a leading cause of death in many parts of Africa (UNAIDS, 2009). The pandemic exacerbates existing health challenges in the region, contributing to high infant mortality rates, low life expectancy, and deepening poverty.

Despite the relatively lower national prevalence rates in Nigeria compared to some other African nations, the disease's large-scale impact on the population due to Nigeria's size is undeniable. Projections between 1986 and 1996 by the WHO Epimodel computer program

showed significant HIV infections, AIDS cases, and deaths, underscoring the country's vulnerability. The increase in HIV prevalence in Nigeria correlates with socio-cultural practices and high rates of sexually transmitted infections (STIs), which continue to drive the spread of HIV (Njue, 2000). This highlights the complex interplay between public health, cultural practices, and disease transmission.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

To better understand the spread and impact of HIV/AIDS, various theoretical frameworks have been employed, including Finke and Schnurrer's Disease Mapping Theory, the Theory of Disease Ecology and Human Behaviour, and the Psycho-Socio-Environmental (PSE) Model.

2.2.1 Finke and Schnurrer's Disease Mapping Theory

Finke and Schnurrer's Disease Mapping Theory, modified by Berghaus (as cited in Roundy, 1980), offers an explanation for the global distribution of diseases such as cholera, tuberculosis, and HIV/AIDS. This theory emphasizes the latitudinal and longitudinal boundaries of diseases, suggesting that the distribution and spread of diseases can be influenced by environmental factors, human behavior, and the ecological context. The theory also highlights the interconnectedness of human populations, vectors, and parasites, underscoring the complex nature of disease transmission, especially in a spatial context. This framework is useful for examining the geographic spread of HIV/AIDS and its varying effects at the individual, community, and national levels.

2.2.2 The Theory of Disease Ecology and Human Behaviour

The Theory of Disease Ecology and Human Behaviour posit that human social, cultural, and individual behaviors significantly affect the survival and spread of disease agents, including HIV. Human actions, cultural practices, and interactions with disease agents play critical roles in both facilitating and mitigating the spread of diseases. The theory divides these behaviors into four main roles: exposure to disease agents, infection transmission through cultural behaviors, the impact of man-made habitats on disease survival, and the diffusion of disease due to human interaction in appropriate habitats (Kocher, 1976). The theory's application to HIV/AIDS focuses on understanding how social and cultural behaviors in specific communities contribute to disease dynamics and epidemiology.

2.2.3 The Psycho-Socio-Environmental (PSE) Model

The Psycho-Socio-Environmental (PSE) Model provides a comprehensive framework for understanding the multiple impacts of HIV/AIDS. This model recognizes the significance of social, environmental, and behavioral factors in shaping health outcomes, beyond just

biological or medical factors. It is complementary to the biomedical model but extends the focus to include social contexts, offering a broader perspective on disease prevention and health maintenance. HIV/AIDS, as a social and health issue, is influenced by various factors such as mobility, social interactions, and healthcare infrastructure, which are especially pertinent in developing countries.

In the context of HIV/AIDS, the PSE model illustrates how disease transmission is not merely a medical issue but a social and environmental one, shaped by cultural practices, social stigma, and economic factors. The model is particularly useful for analyzing the demographic, socio-economic, and socio-cultural effects of HIV/AIDS. It underscores the interconnectedness between the biological, psychological, social, and environmental factors that influence the spread of the disease, making it a valuable tool for this study.

2.3 Demographic Effects of HIV/AIDS

The demographic consequences of HIV/AIDS are profound and multifaceted. The disease significantly alters population dynamics, particularly in terms of mortality and morbidity. Increased mortality rates, particularly among adults in their prime years, have led to a notable shift in population structures. Countries most affected by HIV/AIDS have witnessed a dramatic increase in death rates, with rising funeral costs and a depletion of the working-age population. The epidemic has also caused substantial changes in the structure of households, with many children becoming orphans, further straining the resources of extended family networks.

The impact on life expectancy is particularly severe in Sub-Saharan Africa. In countries like Botswana, Lesotho, and South Africa, life expectancy has dropped sharply due to AIDS-related deaths, and HIV/AIDS has become a leading cause of death, overtaking malaria in many regions (UNAIDS, 2009). The United Nations (2000) analysis revealed that countries with high HIV prevalence have experienced higher mortality rates, particularly among adults aged 15-49, creating a “population chimney” effect, where the population pyramid becomes increasingly skewed, with fewer adults surviving into old age.

Infant and child mortality rates have also been significantly affected by the HIV/AIDS epidemic. Studies in countries like Lesotho, South Africa, and Zimbabwe have shown a substantial increase in mortality rates among children under five, due to mother-to-child transmission of HIV during childbirth or breastfeeding (UNAIDS, 2009). The decline in infant survival rates has reversed progress made in child health over previous decades, compounding the socio-economic challenges faced by families in affected regions.

The mortality impact of HIV/AIDS is evident in Zimbabwe, where adult mortality has tripled between the late 1980s and 1990s, and the mortality rate among young adults is

particularly high. Studies in other African countries have similarly shown that HIV/AIDS has a disproportionately high impact on the young adult population, which has significant demographic and socio-economic implications. In Uganda, projections of future deaths suggest that even with intervention efforts, the cumulative impact of AIDS-related deaths will continue to be felt, particularly among the economically productive age group (Armstrong, 1995).

AIDS-related mortality also has a cascading effect on households, with families facing increased financial strain due to funeral costs, healthcare expenditures, and the loss of income-generating members of the household. Moreover, as the epidemic continues to spread, the socio-cultural fabric of communities is being altered, with increased stigmatization, abandonment, and rejection of individuals living with HIV/AIDS. These demographic shifts have profound implications for family structures, social networks, and community support systems, leading to greater vulnerability, particularly in rural areas.

3. Method

The study area (Benue State) is located between latitudes $6^{\circ}29'$ and $7^{\circ}52'$ North of the equator and longitudes $8^{\circ}20'$ and $9^{\circ}54'$ East of the prime meridian. It consists of seven local government areas: Logo, Ukum, Katsina-Ala, Ushongo, Konshisha, Vandeikya, and Kwande. The region is bounded by Nassarawa State to the north, Taraba State to the north and east, and Cross River to the south (Figure 1).

Figure 1 - Benue State Showing Zone A Representing Eastern Benue State

This study employed a survey research design to collect data on HIV/AIDS from individuals diagnosed as HIV-positive, referred to as People Living with HIV/AIDS (PLWHA), who were receiving care and treatment at selected hospitals. The target population comprised PLWHA actively undergoing treatment at various healthcare facilities within the study area.

An inventory of healthcare facilities within the study area was obtained from the respective Local Government Health Departments. This revealed the existence of 165 public health facilities, 121 private healthcare facilities, and 65 faith-based health centers. Among the public institutions, seven were general hospitals, while the remainder consisted of primary health centers. The faith-based sector included six full-service hospitals and several smaller health centers. Notably, the private healthcare facilities did not participate in HIV/AIDS screening or treatment activities.

According to the pilot survey, only 13 health centers were directly involved in HIV/AIDS screening, care, and treatment. Of these, 8 facilities were randomly selected for inclusion in the study, representing approximately 60% of the total number of eligible healthcare facilities (see Table 1). The sampling frame consisted of 61,679 HIV-positive individuals receiving care across the eight selected hospitals. The sample frame for the study therefore comprised of 61,679 HIV-positive individuals across the eight selected hospitals. The sample size was determined through the Yamane (1967) formula for sample size determination as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where:

- n is the targeted sample size,
- N is the total number of HIV-positive individuals (61,679),
- e is the level of precision (0.05).

Therefore, the study administered questionnaire to 397 respondents distributed proportionally across the selected hospitals based on the number of HIV-positive cases in each facility (table 1).

Table 1: Healthcare Centre handling PLWHA in the Study Area

S/No	Name of Hospitals	L.G.A	Selected Hospital	Patients Screened	Positive Cases	Proportional Sample Size
1.	St. Thomas Hospital, Ihugh	Vandeikya	✓	45,291	7,768	50
2.	GH, Vandeikya	Vandeikya	✓	18,783	7,877	51
3.	NKST Hospital, Mbaakon	Vandeikya				
4.	St. Monica Hospital, Adikpo	Kwande	✓	26,787	5,324	35
5.	GH Adikpo	Kwande				
6.	GH, Katsina-Ala	K-Ala	✓	27,594	11,290	73
7.	St. Anthony Hosp, Zaki-Biam	Ukum	✓	20,256	8,071	52
8.	NKST Hospital, Zaki-Biam,	Ukum	✓	21,226	9,553	62
9.	GH, Sankara,	Ukum				
10.	NKST Hospital, Tor Ayim,	Logo	✓	23,397	8,305	54
11.	GH, Ugba,	Logo				
12.	GH Lesel,	Ushongu	✓	26,192	3,491	23
13	GH, Tse Agberagba,	Konshisha				
	Total		8	209,526	61, 679	400

GH = General Hospital

Source: Authors field work, 2024

Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, with results presented in tables for clarity and ease of understanding. This approach, commonly employed in HIV/AIDS research, allows for a straightforward presentation of key findings without the need for complex statistical methods (Laah, 2002).

To address the study's objectives, a range of data categories were identified and sourced through multiple channels. Demographic and socio-economic characteristics of PLWHA including age, sex, marital status, occupation, religion, ethnicity, number of children, level of education, and income category—were obtained through structured questionnaires administered in the selected hospitals. In addition, information on behavioral and biomedical risk factors associated with HIV transmission was collected. These factors included commercial sex work, multiple sexual partners, same-sex relationships, unprotected sexual intercourse, blood transfusions, and the sharing of needles. Data on the total number of individuals screened for HIV and the number of confirmed HIV/AIDS cases were sourced from both hospital records and participant responses after ethical Clearance from the hospitals and obtaining informed consent from the respondents in collaboration with hospital management involved in the provision of HIV/AIDS care

Furthermore, data on HIV/AIDS-related mortality were collected to enable the calculation of the case fatality rate by comparing the number of recorded deaths to the total number of confirmed HIV-positive cases.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Demographic and Socioeconomic Characteristics of the Respondents (PLWHA)

Table 2 indicates that the respondents' age range was 15-60 years above and a mean age of 37.1 with a standard deviation of 23.56. Most respondents (55.2%) were between 30 and 44 years, a group that is particularly active in farming, which may be impacted by the disease. The study revealed that, majority of respondents living with HIV/AIDS were female (63.2%), with 36.8% being male. This finding aligns with previous studies, such as Anyebe, Hellandendu, and Gyong (2013), which reported a higher prevalence among females.

Most respondents were married (65.0%), with smaller proportions being single (19.9%), divorced (7.8%), widowed (5.0%), or separated (2.3%). Farming was the predominant occupation (46.3%), followed by business (24.7%) and civil service (15.9%). A significant portion of the respondents (75.0%) earned between ₦20,000 to ₦39,000 monthly, with 23.0% earning less than N20,000. The majority had low incomes, which may limit their access to healthcare services, as also found in the study by Anyebe, Hellandendu, and Gyong (2013). The educational levels indicate that majority (58%) had either primary or no formal education whereas, 42% had either primary or tertiary education.

Table 2. Respondents' Demographic and Socioeconomic Characteristics

Variables	Category	N=397	%(100)	Variables	Category	N=397	%(100)
Sex	Male	146	36.8	Marital Status	Single	79	19.9
	Female	251	63.2		Married	258	65.0
Age (in Years)	< 15	5	1.3		Divorced	31	7.8
	15-19	18	4.5		Separated	9	2.3
	20-24	55	13.9		Widowed	20	5.0
	25-29	61	15.4	Education	No Formal	142	35.8
	30-34	147	37.0		Primary	88	22.2
	35-39	27	6.8		Secondary	128	32.2
	40-44	45	11.3		Tertiary	39	9.8
	45-49	17	4.3	Occupation	Casual Labourer	2	0.5
	50-59	16	4.0		Civil Service	63	15.9
> 60	6	1.5	Industrial Worker		1	0.3	
Monthly Income	0 -9,999	23	5.8		Business/Trade	98	24.7
	10,000-19,999	69	17.4		Farming	184	46.3
	20,000-29,999	167	42.1		Sex Worker	2	0.5
	30,000-39,999	130	32.7		Commercial		
	40,000 & above	8	2.0		Driver	3	0.8
					Unemployed	36	9.1
				Others	8	2.0	

Source: Authors Field work, 2024.

4.2 Effects of HIV/AIDS in Benue State

4.2.1 Demographic and Socioeconomic Effects of HIV/AIDS in Benue State

The study revealed that the major demographic effects of HIV/AIDS in the study area includes rising infant and child mortality as opined by 99.5% of the respondents. The increase in infant and child mortality is consistent with global studies, such as those by Bongaarts (2006) and Apata, *et al.*, (2010). These studies reported that millions of children worldwide have lost, or will lose, their parents to HIV/AIDS, which in turn leads to rising mortality among children. The findings are also in line with those of other studies, such as by Jukes *et al.* (2008), which observed that HIV/AIDS has a direct impact on child mortality rates, as affected parents are unable to care for or protect their children adequately. More so, 99.2% of the respondents agreed that rising adult mortality is the second major demographic effect. This agreed with the finding by Nunn *et al.* (2004) which highlight the devastating toll HIV/AIDS takes on the working-age population.

The study revealed imbalance in the male and female ratio of the population opined by 97.7% while 80.4% of the respondents opined that HIV/AIDS result to increase in number of aged people in the population. This is also consistent with previous global studies, such as those by UNAIDS (2006) and Helpage/Aids alliance (2003) which states that 16 million children globally under 15 years have already lost either one or both parents to HIV/AIDS and that another 40 million children will lose their parents within the next 10 years.

Socially, the study indicates that HIV/AIDS has led to an increase in the number of children without parents (94% of respondents). The breakdown in marital relationships (92.7%) and decreased marriage rates (90.9%) are also consistent with the broader literature. Research shows that HIV/AIDS contributes to marital instability due to illness, death, and the stigma surrounding the disease (Tollman *et al.*, 2008). The impact on school enrollment and school dropout rates (88.9%) reflects the broader societal effects of HIV/AIDS, with children often leaving school to care for sick family members or because of financial constraints (Case *et al.*, 2004). The strain on medical facilities and personnel (60.2%) is an expected consequence of the high burden of disease. Similar findings have been reported globally, where healthcare systems, especially in resource-poor settings, are overwhelmed by the demands of managing HIV/AIDS and its complications (Bärnighausen *et al.*, 2007).

Furthermore, HIV/AIDS has also impacted the economic activities and crop production in the study area. The effects include; declining agricultural production (98.7%), food scarcity (98.7%), increased rural urban poverty (98.0%), decline in per capital income (96.0%), and scarcity of essential commodities (79.6%). These might impact food stability and access to balance diet among the population in the study area. These findings mirror those in the literature, where HIV/AIDS has been shown to negatively impact agricultural productivity due to the loss of labor and the disruption of farming activities. As reported by Kofi *et al.* (2014), the epidemic reduces the availability of both skilled and unskilled labour, which in turn affects food production and income generation. Also, HIV/AIDS affects an economy primarily

through increased mortality and morbidity. Resources are often channeled towards treatment, care and support at the detriment of other economic activities (Haacker, 2004). More so, HIV/AIDS has profound effects on the economic situation of those households it afflicts. Income declines as breadwinners fall ill and die and as other household members are obliged to take time off from other productive activities to care for sick relatives. At the same time, households have to reallocate their spending to devote a much greater share to health care and supplies for home care (Haacker, 2002). The loss of productive adults exacerbates economic instability and disrupts families. HIV/AIDS disproportionately affects women, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa, where women are more likely to contract the virus due to social and biological factors (UNAIDS, 2009). This results in a demographic shift, with women often outnumbering men in communities hardest hit by the epidemic.

Furthermore, with younger adults succumbing to the virus, there is a growing reliance on older family members to care for orphans and support their communities (Beegle et al., 2006). This further strains the already burdened social structures, as the elderly often face physical and financial difficulties. The decline in per capita income (96.0%) is also a well-documented effect of HIV/AIDS, as households experience reduced income due to illness and death (Cuddington, 1993). The scarcity of essential commodities (79.6%) further illustrates the ripple effects of the epidemic on local economies, as the disease impedes both production and distribution networks.

Table 3: Demographic and Socioeconomic Effects of HIV/AIDS Benue State

Demographic Effects	N=397	%(100)	Social Effects	N=397	%(100)	Economic Effects	N=397	%(100)
(1) Rising infant and child mortality	395	99.5	Increased number of children without parents	373	94.0	Declining agricultural production	392	98.7
(2) Rising adult mortality	392	99.2	Breakdown in marital relation	368	92.7	Food scarcity	392	98.7
(3) Imbalance in the male/female ratio of the population	388	97.7	Declining primary school enrolment	210	52.9	Increased rural and urban poverty	389	98.0
(4) Increase in number of aged people in the population	319	80.4	Increased withdrawal from school	353	88.9	Decline per capital income	381	96.0
(5) Others	161	40.8	Strain on existing medical facilities and personnel	239	60.2	Scarcity of essential commodities	316	79.6
(6)			Decreased marriage rate	361	90.9	Others	17	4.3
(7)			Increased rural out migration	113	28.5			

Source: Authors field work, 2024

4.2.2 HIV/AIDS Causalities and Gender Crosstabulation in the study area

The findings also reveal the incidence of HIV/AIDS causalities among the respondents. About 51.4% of the respondents lost a family member while 48.6 were not bereaved. Furthermore, among the bereaved respondents, findings indicate that the respondents lost a total of 534 persons to HIV/AIDS. On average, they lost 3 family members each; the males reported losing 3 persons while the females lost 2 persons.

Table 4: Respondents’ Relations Who Died of HIV/AIDS and Gender Crosstabulation

Relations Who Died of HIV/AIDS	Actual Deaths Reported by males	Actual Deaths Reported by females	Total Deaths	Male Respondents	%	Female Respondents	%	Total	%
Non	-	-	-	93	23.4	100	25.2	193	48.6
1-2	57	180	237	38	9.6	120	30.2	158	39.8
3-4	21	39	59.5	6	1.5	11	2.8	17	4.3
7-8	90	90	180	12	3.0	12	3.0	24	6.0
11-12	34	23	57.5	3	0.8	2	0.5	5	1.3
Total	202	332	534	152	38.3	245	61.7	397	100
Average	3	2	3.0						

Source: Authors field work, 2024

4.3 Economic Effects of HIV/AIDS and Gender Crosstabulation

The economic effects of HIV/AIDS include Declining agricultural production, food scarcity, increased poverty, decline per capital income and scarcity of essential commodities as indicated by 79.6 – 98.7% of the respondents on table 5. More so, the effects were felt more by the female respondents compared to the males. This indicates that the female gender were more vulnerable to harsh economic conditions resulting from HIV/AIDS.

Table 5: Economic Effects of HIV/AIDS and Gender Crosstabulation

Economic effects of HIV/AIDS	Gender		
	Male	Female	Total
(a) Declining Agricultural production	144	248	392
	36.3%	62.4%	98.7%
(b) Food scarcity	144	248	392
	36.3%	62.4%	98.7%
(c) Increased rural and urban poverty	138	251	389
	34.8%	63.2%	98.0%
(d) Decline per capita income	143	238	381
	36.0%	60.0%	96.0%
(e) Scarcity of essential commodities	107	209	316
	27.0%	52.6%	79.6%
(f) Others	3	14	17
	.8%	3.5%	4.3%

Source: Authors field work, 2024

4.4 Social Effects of HIV/AIDS and Gender Crosstabulation

Table 6 shows that HIV/AIDS result to increased in the number of orphans as indicated by 94.0% of the respondents. This is common among the female respondents (58.2%) compared to the males (35.8%). Also, majority of the males 59.2% reported breakdown in marital relations as second major social effect of the disease. Similarly, 56.4% of the males opined that HIV/AIDS led to decreased in marriage rate and increased withdrawal from school.

Table 6: Social Effects of HIV/AIDS and Gender Crosstabulation

Social effects of HIV/AIDS	Gender		
	Male	Female	Total
(a) Increased number of children without parents	142	231	373
	35.8%	58.2%	94.0%
(b) Breakdown in marital relations	133	235	368
	33.5%	59.2%	92.7%
(c) Declining primary school enrolment	69	141	210
	17.4%	35.5%	52.9%
(d) Increased withdrawal from school	129	224	353
	32.5%	56.4%	88.9%
(e) Strain on existing medical facilities and personnel	85	154	239
	21.4%	38.8%	60.2%
(f) Decreased marriage rate	137	224	361
	34.5%	56.4%	90.9%
(g) Increased rural out migration	27	86	113
	6.8%	21.7%	28.5%

Source: Authors field work, 2024

5. Conclusion

The study reveals significant demographic, social, and economic impacts of HIV/AIDS in the study area. Demographically, the epidemic has led to a sharp increase in both infant and child mortality, with 99.5% of respondents highlighting this as a major consequence. Similarly, 99.2% of respondents pointed out that rising adult mortality is the second most prominent effect. The epidemic has also contributed to a gender imbalance in the population, with 97.7% of respondents observing a skewed male-to-female ratio. Moreover, the study found that 80.4% of respondents reported a rise in the elderly population, largely due to the loss of younger adults to HIV/AIDS. These findings align with global reports, such as those by Gisslén, et al, (2017) and Helpage/Aids Alliance (2003), which indicate a growing number of orphans and an increasing burden on the elderly to care for vulnerable children.

The social consequences of HIV/AIDS in the study area are equally profound. The epidemic has resulted in a rising number of orphans, with 94% of respondents noting that many

children have lost one or both parents. The study also revealed a breakdown in marital relationships, reported by 92.7% of respondents, as well as a decrease in marriage rates, with 90.9% agreeing with this observation. Furthermore, 88.9% of respondents noted an increase in school withdrawals, as children are forced to leave school to care for sick relatives or due to financial constraints. The strain on medical facilities and personnel, as highlighted by 60.2% of respondents, further underscores the social strain caused by the epidemic. The decline in school enrollment, reported by 52.9% of respondents, points to the longer-term consequences on the education system. These findings are consistent with other research, such as by Tollman et al. (2008) and Case et al. (2004), which discuss the broader social disruption caused by HIV/AIDS.

Economically, the study found that HIV/AIDS has severely impacted agricultural production, with 98.7% of respondents noting a decline in this sector. This has led to food scarcity, as observed by 98.7% of respondents, and contributed to increased rural-urban poverty, highlighted by 98.0% of respondents. The epidemic has also resulted in a decline in per capita income, as reported by 96.0% of respondents, and a shortage of essential commodities, observed by 79.6%. These economic impacts align with findings from studies such as Cuddington (1993) and Kofi et al. (2008), which have documented the negative effects of HIV/AIDS on agricultural productivity and household income.

Given these findings, several policy measures are necessary to address the far-reaching effects of HIV/AIDS. Strengthening healthcare systems is a priority, with a focus on increasing healthcare infrastructure, expanding the availability of antiretroviral treatments, and addressing the shortage of medical personnel. Additionally, supporting orphans and vulnerable children is crucial, with policies that provide access to education, financial assistance, and psychosocial support. Economic interventions should focus on supporting households affected by HIV/AIDS, particularly in agriculture, and promoting sustainable livelihoods. Education policies should prioritize retaining children in school, offering scholarships, school feeding programs, and psychosocial support to mitigate school withdrawals. Furthermore, gender-sensitive interventions are needed to empower women and girls, ensuring they have equal access to healthcare, education, and economic opportunities, particularly in areas disproportionately affected by the epidemic.

In conclusion, the study underscores the importance of a comprehensive approach to addressing the impacts of HIV/AIDS. By strengthening healthcare systems, supporting affected

individuals and families, and promoting economic and educational stability, communities can begin to recover and build resilience against the ongoing challenges posed by the epidemic. These efforts will help mitigate the long-term social and economic impacts of HIV/AIDS, improving the well-being of affected populations and ensuring a more sustainable future.

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